

Strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through religious approach to generate qualified generation

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ABSTRACT

Stunting threatens qualified generation presence and greatly affects the success of a nation's development. The government has used many approaches to reduce the stunting except religious approach whereas in Indonesia as the majority Muslim country, many Indonesians are prone to follow religious leaders rather than a government official. The study obtained a strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through a religious approach. This analytic research used a qualitative approach with case study design. The participants in this research were 62 people namely advocacy, social support, and empowerment target in stunting prevention. The result showed that community empowerment in accelerating stunting prevention has not been optimally implemented. Even social support is adequate but Islamic religious counselors did not receive adequate information about stunting, so they did not optimally convey it back to the community. The policy for accelerating stunting prevention is adequate at the central, provincial, and district levels, however, the policies on religious approaches were limited. Strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through religious approach by using appropriate communication methods and channels such as pre-wedding counseling, Islamic study assemblies, and Friday sermons. Message structure or communication material on stunting prevention should become national policy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's human resource development has not shown encouraging results, which was seen through Indonesia's human development indexes (HDI) rank in 2010 where the Indonesia position is 108th out of 169 countries [1] and after 10 years increased slowly to 107 out of 189 countries [2]. The low HDI is influenced by the low nutritional and health status of the Indonesian people. Islam as a mercy for all nature has perfectly regulated various living arrangements, not only regulating issues related to worship, but also related issues such as human relationships with other humans, other creatures, and their natural surroundings. The existence of relationships proves that Islam does not abandon worldly affairs and does not even separate the problems of the world and the hereafter. Islam in the relationship did not only regulate the economy, socio-culture, politics, agriculture, and technology but also nutrition and public health.

Nutrition and public health problems generally can be prevented by implementing clean and healthy living behavior (CHLB) by Muslim families and all people in Indonesia. Regarding nutrition, knowing the nutritional content of the food consumed will have a direct impact on the amount of nutritional intake. Islam

emphasizes that food consumed by humans must meet two important criteria, namely halal and good. Maintaining a balanced nutritional food intake in the family is the responsibility of married couples. Since in the womb, a mother must maintain the baby's health and growth by consuming nutritious food. Children are a mandate that needs to be properly cared for by fulfilling all their life needs, including nutritional intake. In addition, nutritional problems can be suppressed by promoting health education and nutrition by empowering women for better parenting, increasing family economic status for better food consumption, reducing exposure to infection, and increasing access to health services [3].

Stunting was known short stature is a condition of failure to thrive in children under five years old (toddlers) due to chronic malnutrition and repeated infections, especially in the first 1,000 days of life that last from fetus until child aged 23 months. Children are classified as stunting if their length or height is minus two standard deviations from their normal standard. Stunting refers to the condition of a child's height which is shorter than the height of his age. Chronic malnutrition occurs since the baby is in the womb and the early day after the child is born, but it appears after two years old. Stunting is a state of the very short body that exceeds a deficit of two standard deviations the median length or height of the population based on the standards of the World Health Organization [4].

Several factors that caused stunting include poor parenting practices due to lack of mother's knowledge about health and nutrition before and during pregnancy as well as after the mother gives birth, limited health services including services for mothers during pregnancy and after delivery, limited early learning, limited family access to balanced nutritious food and lack of family access to clean water and sanitation. As adults, stunted children are prone to obesity, making them vulnerable to non-communicable diseases such as heart disease, stroke, or diabetes. Stunting hinders the potential for Indonesia's demographic transition where the ratio of the unemployed rate on working-age population declines. Moreover, it could reduce intelligence level by 5–11 points and cause irreversible brain damage so that nutritional intervention in the First 1,000 Days of Life is a must. In addition, malnutrition can also cause poverty, and based on the research it can cause a gap in income stunting children and normal children by 20%. [5]

The 2016 Global Nutrition Report noted that the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia was ranked 108 out of 132 countries [6]. In the previous report, Indonesia was listed as one out of 17 countries that experienced a double burden, both excess and undernutrition [7]. The results of Basic Health Research, 2018 showed a decrease in stunting prevalence at the national level by 6.4% over five years, from 37.2% (2013) to 30.8% (2018). The stunting prevalence in Lampung Province has also decreased from 42.6% (2013) to 27.3% (2018) [8], which is more than 20% as targeted by WHO. It means that there were still nutritional problems and public health in Lampung Province. Based on the nutrition status monitoring (PSG) of Lampung Province in 2015-2017, the prevalence of stunting in children aged 0-59 months in Pringsewu Regency increased from 21.15% (2015) to 25.78% (2017). The results of the Basic Health Research (Rikesdas) of Lampung Province in 2018 showed that the stunting prevalence in Pringsewu Regency was 20.19%, lower than the last five years result of basic health research 2013 36.99% and it was also the second-lowest district out of 15 districts/cities in Lampung Province, [9] The Indonesian Toddler Nutrition Status Survey (SSGBI) 2019 found that the stunting prevalence at the age of 0-59 months in Pringsewu Regency decreased again to 18.6% [10]

It was necessary to coordinate and involve other sectors and various stakeholders in accelerating stunting prevention such as the central government, local government, another sector, business world, professional organizations, religious organizations, community leaders, religious leaders, the community, and others. The government sectors involved at the central to local levels include the ministry of religion, province religion office, district religion office, and sub-district religion affair office. Efforts to accelerate stunting prevention can be carried out with a health promotion strategy recommended by WHO which consisted of three main strategies: i) advocacy, namely generating political commitment to support policies for health and increasing public awareness and demand for health; ii) empowerment, namely equipping individuals and groups with knowledge, attitudes, and skills that encourage healthy behavior and; iii) social support, namely developing alliances and social support systems that strengthen and encourage healthy behavior as a social norm.

The religious approach in delivering messages to the community is one of the most strategic community empowerment approaches in health promotion, with the application of behavior change communication. As the majority Muslim country, most Indonesians are prone to follow the religious leader's instruction rather than a government official or another leader. They will faithfully follow the religious leader's instruction without condition. Empowering religious leader in stunting prevention is very important to support public behavior change. Behavior change communication is an interactive process to design various messages using various media and channels to promote, change, develop and maintain positive behavior, especially in this case public health behavior. Health communication rooted in the fields of education and health promotion is strongly influenced by psychology, communication, and various other behavioral disciplines, especially theories and models of health behavior based on psychology science [11].

Even the community understands about a balanced nutritional diet, parenting, and clean and healthy living behavior however they did not implement it optimally in daily life so that there are still many nutritional problems for toddlers, especially stunting. That is the important reason to conduct further and in-depth research on this issue.

The purpose of this study was to analyze, develop and formulate a strategy to accelerate stunting prevention through a religious approach to generate qualified generation. The specific objectives were: i) to find out and analyze more deeply about behavior change communication through religious approach applied in accelerating stunting prevention as a community empowerment strategy; ii) to find out and analyze more deeply about efforts to create an atmosphere that supported the implementation of community empowerment related to stunting prevention through community leaders and religious leaders by implementing social support strategies; iii) to find out and analyze more deeply about the implementation of advocacy strategies to the policymakers at various levels, especially in the religious sector to increase active participation of all sectors in accelerating stunting prevention.

The benefits of this research were: i) it was hoped that it can increase knowledge, experience, and application for scholars on the existing theories, especially the science of developing Islamic society generally and especially for the community and as reference material and ideas for future research in the field of Islamic community development, health promotion, religious approaches in health communication and the acceleration of stunting prevention; ii) it was hoped to be used as a source of information for the government and the community as well as comparison material to make decisions on the implementation of community empowerment strategy, social support, and advocacy in accelerating stunting prevention through religious approach to generate qualified generation.

This research was carried out on February to July 2021; located in three regional levels, namely: Provincial Level at Lampung Province, District Level at Pringsewu District, and Subdistrict Level (selected based on the criteria for locus area for stunting intervention): i) Priority I Pagelaran Subdistrict, ii) Priority II Gadingrejo Subdistrict, and iii) Priority III Sukoharjo Subdistrict.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This was qualitative research employed a case study design. In this study, data collection was carried out using in-depth interviews and focus group discussions (FGD), observation, and document review. In-depth interviews are a group of unstructured interviews which are often also called intensive interviews, qualitative interviews, ethnographic interviews, and open-ended interviews [12]. From the results of this study, it is expected to be able to formulate in detailed and systematic strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through a religious approach to generate qualified generation.

Informants in this study were selected by using a purposive sampling technique. The informants were determined intentionally based on the criteria or purposive samples [13]. In this study, the selection of informants was based on the following criteria and considerations: i) in charge of units that have the authority as policymakers, budgeting planning, and monitoring the implementation of stunting prevention acceleration, they act as the target of advocacy; ii) people who are involved in creating an atmosphere that supports the implementation of accelerating stunting prevention, act as the target of social support; iii) prospective bride, groom, women of reproductive age, health cadres, mothers of toddlers, members of Islamic study assembly. They act as implementers (subjects) and targets (objects) for community empowerment in accelerating stunting prevention.

There were two instruments in this research. For collecting primary data, we used FGD guidelines and in-depth interviews as well as an observation checklist/document tracing and for the secondary data, we collected from reports, profiles, marriage books, and maternal and child handbook/health cards. The data collection procedure is carried out through in-depth interviews, a checklist of documents to be explored, a check of observation, and focus group discussion (FGD). The target of the in-depth interview is the stakeholder in stunting prevention at the district level. Document verification and observation of the informant institution were performed after an in-depth interview. FGDs were conducted with a religious counselor, health promotion officers, and nutritionist at the health centers in three sub-districts. And finally, the researcher met the expert to confirm the finding. The expert included the Head of Lampung Province Religion Office, universities, and Islamic organizations.

The data collected were processed to obtain a draft of the result matrix so that it was known whether we need for further data collection including both types and sources of information as well as enriching the information that needed to explore more including the sources of information another (snowball) until the data is saturated. This is one of the efforts to validate the information by triangulating the types of data and existing data sources. In addition to data triangulation, a confirmability test was also carried out by confirming the figures and actors involved in the implementation of marriage counseling and coaching in

Islamic study assemblies and Friday sermons. The resulting data is reduced by using abstraction which is an effort to summarize the statements that need to be maintained. Then arrange them in units. At the final stage, the data validity was checked. The analysis or interpretation of the result data and information was aligned with the research objectives. Data reduction and abstraction had been carried out, the result displayed data in the form of brief descriptions, charts, relationships between categories, and so on. By displaying data, it will be easier to understand what is happening and to plan further work based on the finding. Then the result was concluded and verified

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to Central Bureau of Statistics, Lampung Province consisted of 15 district/city, 228 sub-districts, 205 sub-sub districts and 2,449 villages. The total population of Lampung Province in 2020 was 9,007,848 people, consisting of 4,616,805 men and 4,391,043 women [14]. Pringsewu District has an area of about 625 km². Since established in 2013 Pringsewu was divided into nine sub-districts, 126 villages and five sub-sub districts and the population in 2020 was 403,115 people. The population composition of Lampung Province in 2020 based on their religion were Islam 7,552,868 people (83.24%), Protestant 177,459 (1.96%), Catholic 146,605 (1.62%), Hindu 1,053,120 (11.61%), Buddhists 143,743 people (1.58%) and others 85 people (0.001%), while in Pringsewu District were Islam 370,756 people (92.6%), Protestant 2,873 people (0.72%), Catholic 10,385 people (2.59%), Hindu 11,165 people (2.79%) and Buddha 5,215 people (1.30%) [15].

3.1. Community empowerment

The results of this study showed that community empowerment in accelerating stunting prevention in the regions was inadequate. This is illustrated by the understanding about stunting conveyed by the informant who is a mother of a toddler and as health cadres and member of the Islamic study assembly:

"... Yes, I just heard about it, he said if you were tall, wasn't it??..." (I-6)

Other informants, namely prospective brides who are women of reproductive age, mostly provide a picture of a lack of understanding about stunting. Only some prospective brides and groom had few understandings about stunting:

".. It's a matter of development like that or not, growth and developmental, nutrition problems are related to development..." (I-7)

In the delivery of information or communication through religious approach about stunting, there are several ways to be done. There are very potential and effective in marriage counseling activities or prospective bride and groom courses. The other ways are Islamic study assembly and Friday sermons as well as community development programs by the religious counselor as stated:

".... with the existence of pre-wedding counseling, before like that, yes, then every Islamic study assembly, the moments of those meeting, and it is not wrong if we have a Friday sermon schedule, it can be delivered through that, and incidentally we have programs for the religious counselor because they visited several, one of the programs was monitoring program related to the health in the community..." (I-35)

The community generally understands the causes of stunting such as lack of nutritional intake, lack of parenting, lifestyle, and poor sanitation. Another informant who is a prospective bride and a woman of reproductive age said that the cause of stunting is related to nutritional intake and parenting. This is supported by several research results that stated the cause of stunting related to the history of parenting in nutrition which consisted of three factors namely colostrum, pre-lacteal feeding, and exclusive breastfeeding [16].

Regarding nutritional intake in Islam, Islam has regulations on halalan tayyiban or halal and good food. Good food is food that meets hygiene requirements and is also halal. Human consumed food to maintain their survival. This showed that Islam and health both have the same goal for the good of mankind.

WHO recommended increasing public knowledge and understanding through community-based work programs for nutrition education and promotion in the context of interventions to improve maternal, newborn, and child health through community services and stunting prevention. The work program includes behavior change communication and strategies for community mobilization by trained health workers or community cadres and implemented in homes, villages, or community groups [17].

In implementing behavior change communication and community mobilization strategies at home, community groups, and at the village or sub-district scope, the communication techniques used must be adjusted. For the behavior change communication at home or in the family, in community groups and the scope of the village or sub-district used interpersonal communication, group communication, and public communication respectively [18].

3.2. Social support

In general, community leaders and religious leaders viewed that the socialization efforts were not carried out optimally, as described by one of the informants:

"...yes, it's good enough, but maybe it just needs to be intensified, so it's just a massive acceleration about it, e... especially to reach the bottom of the community, isn't it? ..."

Another informant from the FGD shared an illustration that the Islamic religious counselor had not received adequate information about stunting, as mentioned by the informant:

".... religious counselors have never been given information by health centers about stunting ..."

The religious approach used in the delivery of information by community leaders, religious leaders, and health workers has been proven to be effective in mobilizing community empowerment in the health program such as the community-based total sanitation (CBTS) program which encourages people to own and have access to sanitation facilities namely toilet and clean water. This program is also closely related to stunting prevention as explained by informants:

"...a similar pattern has been proven to be powerful and effective yeah... it works..." (I-14)
"...Islamic Organizations and Religious Leaders became the launcher/team for the District CBTS, for healthy sanitation, at that time they collaborated with Stichting Nederlandse Vrijwilligers (SNV) a community social institution that collaborated with the Dutch. At that time, outside the forum, the chairman of SNV approached me, Mas Bambang, and others. Like this, the same as what you asked, what are the taken approaches to solve Pringsewu to become open defecation free ..." (I-19c)

Islamic religious counselors have an important role in empowering the community and as government employees. Success in education and counseling to the community indicates success in self-management. Islamic education and counseling materials are all Islamic teachings which are the main sources are the Qur'an and al-Hadith. However, it must be focused on the points that are important and needed by the target community. The scope of the material includes Islamic religious material and cross-sectoral development material. The cross-sectoral development materials cover the fields of supporting materials, namely Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution and laws and regulations needed by the target community; materials for increasing knowledge and public education, materials for improving family and community welfare; materials for improving family nutrition and public health counseling materials [19]. The results of previous study [20] showed that theoretically, various concepts in Islam are very possible to be integrated into health promotion models in changing public health behavior. This integration concept can be applied to assist health to increase effectively public health status and to the right target.

3.3. Policy advocacy

Government policies related to the acceleration of stunting prevention at the provincial and district levels were adequate, but at the sub-district level they were still inadequate. This is in accordance with the research that showed the government's role in overcoming stunting was not optimal. It can be seen through the health center and stakeholder intervention, lack of stunting budget, lack of cooperation among stakeholder, lack of health promotion on nutrition, stakeholder did not understand about stunting and stunting problem in their area. The government and stakeholder in the village did not intervened stunting problem optimally and did not commit to prevent stunting [21].

The policies related to religious approaches and examples of the role of the Ministry of Religion in preventing and handling stunting at the provincial district level and sub-district such as the role of Sub District Religion Affair, Islamic religious counselor, Health Information and education for prospective brides and groom, religious school, Islamic study assembly, Friday sermons and marriage sermons were stated by the informant:

"... one of the policies is eee... with the pre-marital coaching previously like that, yes, then every Islamic study assembly, the moments of Islamic study assembly then eee it's not wrong if we have a Friday sermon schedule..." (I-35)

"...through Friday sermons and marriage counseling..." (I-40)

From the results of the research, it is known that the marriage guidance or prospective bride and groom courses carried out by the Sub District Religion Affair Office and the District Religion Office have quoted several materials on health, especially reproductive health. Unfortunately, in the context of stunting prevention, religious counselors had not systematically conveyed it. This happens because their guidelines in counseling didn't contain material on the acceleration of stunting prevention. Marriage counseling program is the right choice to be used as a tool to support stunting prevention and reduction program at the upstream level because it can be used to convey various materials that are closely related to current issues in health, such as reproductive health, family economic preparation, and parenting patterns. While this time the marriage counseling material covered preparing a harmonious family, building relationships in the family, meeting family needs, maintaining reproductive health, and preparing quality generations [22].

Based on the study results, it was known that the monitoring and guiding of the Islamic study assembly and Friday sermons carried out by the Sub District Religion Affair Office and District Religion Office of Religion Ministry have directed some material content to quote health issues. However, the material related to stunting prevention was not conveyed by the religious counselor, lecturers, and preachers in their speech. This also happened because there were no counseling or communication guidelines to accelerate stunting prevention. Islamic study assembly was one of the community education institutions organized from, by, and for the community which has a role to foster the quality of the people in various aspects of life ranging from education to social control of the people [20].

3.4. Strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through religious approach

Islam obliges its people to prepare the next qualified generation carried out by the Islam people themselves. As the word of Allah SWT in the letter Ar-Rad verse 11 which means "*Indeed Allah does not change the condition of a people until they change the situation that is in themselves*" and Islam also forbids its people to leave the weak descendants, this is as Allah SWT said in Surah an-Nisa verse 9 which means "*and fear Allah those who, if they leave behind them, weak children*". In addition, everyone must maintain their health, as revealed in the words of the Prophet Muhammad, "*Indeed, your body has a right over you*". Four main things must be possessed by a qualified young generation, namely the quality of faith, intellectual (science), good deeds (morals) social (the art of socializing) [23].

Previous research [24] showed that based on evidence in Indonesia, the causes of stunting were identified due to the low-level of mother's education or knowledge, premature birth, and birth length, exclusive breastfeeding for six months and household socioeconomic status. In addition, drinking water or clean water is very important for households equipped with healthy toilets to reduce stunting. Another study [25] concluded that the determinants of stunting are the mother and father's knowledge, household socioeconomic status, sanitation conditions, access to maternal health services, and family planning.

3.4.1. Pattern of balanced nutrition

The first thousand days of life (FTDL) are very important to overcome stunting, that is why the women get pregnant they must get adequate nutrition because it greatly affects children born to experience stunting or not. FTDL is the initial period of life that begins since the child is in the womb. The influence of several factors is the direct cause of stunting affecting the children's nutritional status. FTDL is very important because it is the most optimal growth period for a child. Mothers who experience malnutrition and lack of energy during pregnancy are called chronic energy deficiency (CED) pregnant women. The mother who has good knowledge can prevent stunting started from pregnancy by consuming nutritious food to prevent low birth weight, providing good parenting for their children after delivery and providing balanced nutrition for their children [26]. Nutrition and food intake has a big role in fostering and maintaining a baby's health. In the letter 'Abasa verse 24 there is a very clear command: "*So let people pay attention to their food*".

The command to eat which is mentioned in the Qur'an 27 times always emphasizes two things namely halal (permissible) and tayyib (good). Four verses combined these two characteristics (halal and tayyib), namely Surah al-Baqarah verse 168, al-Ma'idah verse 88, al-Anfal verse 69, and an-Nahl verse 114. The food eaten should be met these two criteria. Rasulullah SAW taught not to eat before feeling hungry and stop eating before you feel full, as Rasulullah SAW said: "*We are people who don't eat until we feel hungry, and if we eat, we don't get full*." This hadith also taught the importance of eating time because it takes around three or four hours to digest food in the digestive tract so that after eating time, a person will feel hungry again and have an appetite. The Messenger of Allah (PBUH) has emphasized this and at the same time

explained the limit of excessive that is prohibited, as he said: "*Including excessive behavior is when you eat everything you want*". Previous research [27] showed that parents with bad habit parenting will increase the risk of stunting so that family-based intervention in feeding parenting is very important to reduce stunting.

3.4.2. Parenting style

Family factors related to stunting in Indonesia are low parenting education, low family welfare, malnutrition during pregnancy, bad sanitation and inadequate water supply, father smoking, young maternal and bad parenting [28]. Food quality in the view of religion must be halal and good. Halal is from the aspect of acquisition and good is from the aspect of food substances. Good food is containing substances that needed by the human body. In this context, it is interesting to pay attention to the hadith of the Prophet SAW as narrated by 'Ubadah bin al-Walid bin 'Ubadah bin as-Samit which means: "*Give your children food as you eat and give them clothes as you wear*". The hadith clearly emphasized that parents pay attention to their children. If they ignored their children's development condition, religion considers it as a sin. This is expressly stated by the Prophet Muhammad, which means: "*It is enough for a person to sin if he ignores the people who are his dependents*".

One of the efforts to monitor the growth and development of infants and toddlers is through weighing infants and toddlers monthly at the integrated post or health workers. This is part of good parenting to prevent nutritional problems especially stunting to their children. Baby and under-five growth and development monitoring are performed by measuring weight and height regularly every month. The research revealed that the parent's role and function are to nurture their children including growth and development monitoring [29].

3.4.3. Clean and healthy life behaviour

Cleanliness is part of Islam as the hadith narrated by Abu Hurairah, "*Clean everything as much as you can. Indeed, Allah Ta'ala built this Islam based on cleanliness and nobody will enter paradise except every clean person*" (H.R at-Tabrani). Cleanliness is also a part of faith as mentioned in the hadith "*Cleanliness is part of faith*" (HR Muslim). The main personal hygiene associated with stunting is washing hands with soap. Mothers with bad habits of handwashing have a higher risk to get stunted children.

The Qur'an has given instructions specifically on the importance of paying attention to eating patterns and food types concerning the development and maintenance of health, since the beginning of baby life (post-birth). The Qur'an talked about the importance of breastfeeding mother's milk (BMM) which is not only halal and tayyib but also very necessary for the mother's and baby's health. The breastfeeding campaign program for stunting preventions was following the instructions and recommendations of the Qur'an. As Allah SWT said in Al-Baqarah verse 233 which means "*Mothers should breastfeed their children for two full years, which is for those who want to perfect breastfeeding*". Breast milk with various stages of administration to infants and children (0-24 months) will prevent stunting. This is in accordance with the research [30] that showed involving religious leaders in socialization regarding ideal age for marriage, good parenting, and sanitation hygiene are supporting stunting prevention. Related to child parenting, including early breastfeeding initiation, giving exclusive breastmilk for up to six months and continued with complement feeding up to two years will help babies and children to grow optimally. Another research [31] recommended the strategy to accelerate stunting prevention after delivery should include a multilevel strategy to support the mother to breastfeed their babies.

Water is the main means of cleaning and purity. In the sense that cleanliness means essential, water is mentioned by the Qur'an in 63 verses, besides those mentioned about the sea, rivers, and clouds that all have correlation with water. Water has multi-functional uses to support human health. Some research findings in Indonesia have similarities with findings from abroad which revealed that drinking water that is not managed safely and came from safe sources will increase the incidence of stunting in children under five.

The Messenger of Allah said: "*Fear the three cursed places, excrete dirt in flowing water sources, on roads, and in shelters*" (H.R Abu Dawud and Ibn Majjah). The source of flowing water is a river, meaning that it is prohibited to throw dirt including feces into the river, either directly or by flowing it through pipes, ditches, ponds, or other things which finally end into rivers. By its nature, water will flow to a lower place; rivers originating from the mountains will flow far to the estuary and into the sea. At the riverside, there will be a lot of people who used water for various purposes of life. If water is polluted by dirt or feces, it will cause and spread various diseases such as diarrhea which is one of the direct causes of stunting. The number of deaths due to diarrhea is 1.8 million people every year. Previous study in Ambon [32] explained that water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), and low birth weight status are the risk factors of stunting for the children aged 7–26 months.

Smoking behavior affects the health and nutritional status of the family, as the research [32] stated that cigarette smoke from the smoking parent has a direct impact on the children's growth and development

by disturbing the nutrition absorption to the children. This result is supported by a previous study conducted by Semba *et al.* [33] which found that tobacco used by parents was the risk factor for malnutrition in children living in poor families in an urban area, Indonesia. Based on the hadith narrated by Abu Dawud that the Messenger of Allah forbade everything that intoxicates and weakens. In the past, people thought that *khamer* (alcoholic beverage) contained several health benefits, but currently, science had proven that it has only less benefit rather than goodness. This category included various types of narcotics, drugs, and other addictive substances. According to some scholars, smoking is forbidden for health reasons and its addictive effects. Cigarette smoke contains about 4,000 chemicals and causes at least 25 types of diseases ranging from deadly ones such as cancer, heart, lung, to troublesome ones such as impotence and pregnancy disorders.

4. CONCLUSION

The effort to prevent stunting was regulated by Islam and attached functionally to every Muslim, based on the spirit to follow the order of Allah SWT as mentioned in Surah An-Nisa verse 9 that Islam prohibits their followers leave weak generation. It underlies the novelty of this research namely the strategy for accelerating stunting prevention through a religious approach is proposed to be national policy. This approach are: i) based on communication methods and channels, namely marriage counseling or prospective bride and groom courses, Islamic study assemblies and Friday sermons; ii) based on message structure or communication material for stunting prevention acceleration with Islamic religious language. It can be used as guidelines or guidelines by Islamic religious counselor, health promotor and nutritionist, and family planning counselor.

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